

BOUNDARY ELEMENTS ANALYSIS OF THE OFF-AXIS SPECIMEN

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ABSTRACT

The off-axis tension test used for the determination of G_{12} presents some difficulties derived from the coupling between the boundary conditions and the stress state at the gauge length, so that an accurate stress analysis is required. Due to the fact that only a reduced part of the domain is of interest and also due to the presence of singularities in some boundary conditions, the Boundary Element Method has been considered very appropriate to deal with this problem. A program based on this method has been developed to study orthotropic behaviour. In this paper stresses and displacements along the boundary are studied for different boundary conditions as well as the influence of the fiber orientation angle on the deformation in the specimen.

1.-INTRODUCTION

The off-axis tension test is characterized by a coupling between extension and shear deformations which give rise to a non-uniform stress field in the specimen test section. The test section stress field depends upon the specimen gripping conditions, the geometry and the material properties. The non-uniform stress field gives rise to difficulties in obtaining accurate and consistent shear modulus values. To overcome this problem, numerical, experimental and combined numerical and experimental techniques have been developed, and correction factors have been proposed to account for the non-uniform stress field, Pindera and Herakovich (1), Cañas, París and Marín (2), as well as a special grip system, Sun and Berreth (3).

The Finite Element Method has usually been employed to evaluate the effect of the specimen gripping constraint upon the strains recorded in the specimen section. However, the presence of singularities at the grips, under certain constraint conditions, can reduce the efficacy of this numerical technique. Additionally the necessity of local refinements of the mesh to take account of high gradients of stresses can be highly time-consuming in the data preparation procedure.

The Boundary Element Method handles as independent variables the boundary displacements and the boundary stress vector, and high gradients of stresses are easy to model. Additionally, mesh refinements do not require lengthy data preparation time, the method being ideally suited to account for local effects such as the presence of singularities. For this reason it is straightforward to investigate the effect of various constraint conditions on the displacement and stresses along the boundary.

The method calculates on the domain variables at a second stage once the problem has been solved in the boundary. In this case information is only required in a reduced area (the gauge length), this

calculation is not time-consuming from the point of view of either data preparation or computation time.

In this paper a boundary element program developed to analyze general two-dimensional configurations for orthotropic materials is presented. The program is used to study a 10 degree off-axis tension test for a graphite-epoxy specimen under different boundary conditions. The influence of the fiber orientation angle on certain variables of the problem is also studied.

2.- THE BOUNDARY ELEMENT METHOD FOR ORTHOTROPIC MATERIALS.

The Boundary Element Method is based on Somigliana's Identity, which allows the displacements to be expressed at an internal point of a domain in terms of an integral representation of the displacements and the stress vector along the boundary, adopting the following expression in the absence of body forces:

$$u_j(x) + \int_{\partial D} T_{ji}^{0\psi}(x,y) u_i^b(y) ds(y) = \int_{\partial D} \psi_{ji}^0(x,y) t_i^b(y) ds(y) \quad x \in D \quad y \in \partial D \quad (1)$$

where, with reference to Figure 1a:

- $u_j(x)$ represents the displacement at the internal point x along direction j .
- $u_i^b(y)$ and $t_i^b(y)$ represent, respectively, the displacement and component of the stress vector along direction i at point y of the boundary.
- $\psi_{ji}^0(x,y)$, $T_{ji}^{0\psi}(x,y)$ represent the fundamental solution of the two dimensional Kelvin problem for an orthotropic material, being the displacement / component of the stress vector along direction i at point y originated by a unit load at point x along direction j .

Figure 1 Definition of the problem: a) geometry b) discretization

The expressions for ψ_{ji}^0 and $T_{ji}^{0\psi}$ can be found in Doblare, Espiga, Gracia y Alcantud (4). It must be stressed that they are expressed in the principal orthotropic axes of the material, the subindexes i and j , which appear in equation (1), representing these axes.

If point x is taken to the boundary the former expression is transformed into:

$$C_{ij}^0(x) u_i^b(x) + \int_{\partial D} T_{ji}^{0\psi}(x,y) u_i^b(y) ds(y) = \int_{\partial D} \psi_{ji}^0(x,y) t_i^b(y) ds(y) \quad x, y \in \partial D \quad (2)$$

where C_{ij}^0 , usually called the free term, has the following expression:

$$C_{ij}^0(x) = \delta_{ij} + \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} u_i^b(x) \int_{\partial D_\epsilon} T_{ji}^{0\psi}(x,y) ds(y) \quad (3)$$

Equation (2) is similar to (1) but involves only variables along the boundary, point x where the equation is written (usually called the collocation point), now being on the boundary. This fact gives rise to singularities in the kernels of the two integrals which appear in the integral equation, that corresponding to the first one being required to be interpreted and calculated in the sense of the Cauchy principal value.

Replacing the domain ∂D by an approximated one ∂D_k formed by a set of K rectilinear elements and assuming a linear evolution of the variables (displacements and stresses) along each of these elements, equation (2) can be written in the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & C_{ij}(l) u_i(l) + \sum_{k=1}^K \int_{\partial D_k} T_{ji}^{\sigma \psi}(\xi, l) \begin{bmatrix} N_1(\xi) & N_2(\xi) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_1(\xi) & N_2(\xi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_{1,k}^b(k) \\ u_{1,k}^b(k+1) \\ u_{2,k}^b(k) \\ u_{2,k}^b(k+1) \end{Bmatrix} ds_k = \\
 & = \sum_{k=1}^K \int_{\partial D_k} \psi_{ji}^{\sigma}(\xi, l) \begin{bmatrix} N_1(\xi) & N_2(\xi) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_1(\xi) & N_2(\xi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} t_{1,k}^b(k) \\ t_{1,k}^b(k+1) \\ t_{2,k}^b(k) \\ t_{2,k}^b(k+1) \end{Bmatrix} ds_k
 \end{aligned} \quad 1, k \in \partial D_k; x \in \partial D_k \quad (4)$$

where l is the node on the boundary where the pair of integral equations are applied, N_1 and N_2 are the linear interpolation functions on the integration element k and $u/t^b_{k(k+1)}$ represent, for instance, the displacement/component of the stress vector at the node $k+1$ as belonging to the element k .

The application of this equation leads to a system of equations which can be written symbolically in the form:

$$H_{rs} u_s = G_{rs} t_s \quad r, s = 1, 2, k \quad (5)$$

The application of the boundary conditions leads to a system of equation whose solution generates the displacements and stress vector along the boundary. Consequently equation (1) conveniently discretized in a similar form to equation (2) can now be used to calculate displacements at the internal points desired.

The main problems in applying the method, from a computational point of view, are in the calculation of the integrations along the element where the collocation point is and in the computation of the free term. In this program both difficulties are solved together by applying a rigid body displacement. Further aspects of the general application of the method can be found in Alarcón, Martín and París (5) and more extensively in Brebbia, Telles and Wrobel (6). Particular applications to orthotropic materials can be found in Vable and Sikarskie (7) and in (4).

3.- APPLICATION TO THE OFF-AXIS TENSION TEST

The geometry and the properties of the material which correspond to a typical graphite-epoxy composite are represented in Figure 2.

The boundary conditions to be considered are represented in Figure 3. Boundary conditions 3a correspond to the ideal case being taken as reference. The clamped case is represented in 3b, case 3c including the possibility of a lateral (transverse) displacement between the two extremes of the

specimen, a situation considered in order to model a possible action of the grip system. 174 elements have been used to model the boundary, this number being determined by the refinement of the mesh close to the vertexes of the specimen in order to take into account the presence of singularities in the stress vector, at the corners, associated with the clamped sides. Singular elements have not been used, due to the lack of knowledge of the order of the singularity at these points. No singularities appear in the ideal case, such a fine mesh not being required, although the same mesh has been used just for comparison purposes. In fact, having used linear elements, only four elements (not considering problems associated with the integrations), would be necessary for the correct modelling of the problem.

Figure 3 a) simply supported case, b) clamped case, c) clamped case allowing transversal relative displacements.

The presence of singularities can be first of all observed in the distribution of the normal stress along the clamped edge. Three cases corresponding to the angles $\theta = 0, 10$ and 30 are included in Figure 4, the external action in all of them being a longitudinal uniform displacement along one end of 0.00512 cm. This value is associated with a resultant load of 200 pounds for the 10 degree case making the results comparable with those corresponding to other boundary conditions.

Figure 4. Normal stress along the clamped end for three different fiber orientation angles.

In all cases the presence of the singularity is clear, the order in both corners only being symmetric when the fiber is oriented in the same direction as the load or perpendicular to them, although this case has not been included in the Figure. When the fibers have a certain angle of orientation with respect to the load, a more severe state of stress appears at the corner corresponding to the side towards which the fibers are oriented. This fact has a clear explanation, as shown in Figure 5. The natural tendency of the specimen is to deform in the way indicated in a). A bending moment is generated as a reaction in order to fulfill the displacement requirements. This bending moment generates, as indicated in b), traction stresses at points close to the top which increase those already existing due to the applied load.

Figure 5. The mechanism of non-symmetrical normal stresses.

It must be mentioned that higher values than those represented in Figure 4 appear in the numerical solution (17000 in the 10 degrees case), but have not been included in order to make it more representative. The lower value of the induced stresses for a fixed external displacement at one end, when increasing the fiber angle orientation, is due to the increment in flexibility of the specimen with the angle.

Figure 6 represents the distribution of the tangential stresses along the clamped end, showing a similar qualitative tendency to the normal reaction distribution.

Figure 6 Tangential stress along the clamped end for three different fiber orientation angles.

The representation of the displacements along the boundary makes it easier to understand the behaviour of the specimen under different grip conditions. Figure 7 shows the longitudinal displacements along the two free edges of the specimen (upper and lower) for the three boundary conditions described in Figure 3. The results are made comparable by applying the same resultant load at the ends of the specimen, 200 pounds in the cases shown. In the simply supported case this load is applied uniformly distributed and in the other two cases a certain uniform longitudinal displacement is applied, scaling the results as required according to the resultant value of the induced reactions.

Figure 7 Longitudinal displacements along the lateral sides.

The results corresponding to the simply supported case coincide with those predicted by the lamination theory, the difference in longitudinal displacements between the top and the bottom of the specimen being constant along the specimen. The clamped conditions lead only to a slightly stiffer specimen (10%) in the longitudinal direction although a clear restraint effect appears along the central zone of the specimen, where the relative longitudinal displacement considered reaches a maximum, being at the center some 80 % greater at the top than at the bottom. The case allowing transverse relative displacements leads to a solution which produces almost uniform longitudinal displacements throughout any section. The explanation of this fact is that a rigid body motion can relate the deformed shape corresponding to the simply supported case Figure 8a and to the clamped case allowing transverse displacements, Figure 8b. It has to be emphasized that the two ends of the specimen are rigidly clamped, the relative lateral displacement allowed the possibly of representing an external degree of freedom from the combined jaws and specimen.

Figure 8 Deformed configuration a) simply supported case b) clamped case allowing transverse relative displacements

Displacements at internal points can be calculated applying equation (1) conveniently discretized. Figure 9 shows the longitudinal displacements, associated with the clamped case, across a transverse line at the center of the specimen for three values of the fiber orientation angle.

Figure 9 Distribution of the longitudinal displacements across a central transverse line.

An almost linear distribution appears for all the fiber angles, which prompts the representation of the angle defining this distribution as a function of the fiber angle orientation. Figure 10 represents this variation showing that the maximum values of the angle twisted by the central lines are reached for fiber orientation angles between 10 and 15 degrees.

Figure 10 Sheared angle in the central section versus the fiber orientation angle.

4.- CONCLUSIONS

A numerical technique based on the Boundary Element Method has been developed to handle the analysis of orthotropic materials. The application to the case of the off-axis tension-test has allowed the influence of different constraint conditions at the specimen ends on the deformed shapes to be studied, the existence and relative strength of the singularities also being analyzed.

An interesting relation between the bending effect in the clamped case (measured as the angle sheared by the section) and the orientation angle of the fibers has also been obtained, the maximum values lying between 10 and 15 degrees of the fiber orientation.

The code developed represents an excellent tool for analyzing any problem related to composite materials with an orthotropic configuration, which offers the possibility of studying laminates formed by laminae oriented in the same direction or perpendicularly. Its suitability for taking into account local effects such as the presence of singularities makes the approach appropriate for the study of problems like the Iosipescu test where the grip condition causes singularities and where only a reduced part of the domain (the central section) is of interest.

An extension dealing with anisotropic laminates will be of great interest in order to handle with laminates such as $[+\theta, -\theta]$.

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